

A Linear Sorter Core based on a Programmable Register File

Lluís Ribas, David Castells, Jordi Carrabina

Abstract—Hardware sorters exploit inherent concurrency to improve the performance of sequential, software-based sorting algorithms. They are usually based on Batcher’s odd-even or bitonic merging networks to attenuate the area-greedy hardware solutions. In this paper, a new hardware sorter architecture built on a programmable register file is presented. It is inspired on insertion sorting algorithms and composed of as many data-slice cells as data to sort. Such sorters are easily expandable and require minimal control schemes. As a result, they can better area-time performance of other sorters. Besides, they can serve as a core module for massive-data management applications.

Index Terms— Hardware sorter, insert sort architecture, parallel computing, sorting, sorting networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

SORTER circuits play an important role in many applications in the digital signal processing domain and, of course, in the data-base management, especially for information searching and retrieval.

For such applications, either speed, volume of data, or both hinder the use of conventional, well-known sequential sorting algorithms [6] which are programmed for being executed on single processor, von Neumann’s architecture machines. Therefore alternative parallel architectures [1], [5] have broadly been used to overcome the inherent limitations of common computers.

The idea of using parallel computing to solve a given problem is to achieve a significant time complexity reduction by increasing the number of processing elements (PE). Again, though, the overall complexity remains the same but time is divided by the number of PE.

As in the sequential algorithms, optimizing the sorting method implies some overhead, i.e. increasing the complexity constants. While this might not be an issue in parallel computing, it is a matter of careful study when the sorter is implemented completely in hardware [2], [11].

In this work, we developed a hardware sorter with a simple architecture that minimizes area overhead, especially for applications where progressive sorting is required; i.e. to obtain the greatest scores out of a large volume of them.

Next section overviews other hardware architectures for

This work has been supported by the *Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología* under grant MCYT-TIC2001-2508.

The authors are with the *Centre de Prototips i Solucions Hardware-Software* (CEPHIS) and the Computer Science Department of the *Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona* (UAB), ETSE, Campus UAB, 08193 Bellaterra, Spain. (Phone: +34 935 811 078; fax: +34 9353033; e-mails: {Lluís.Ribas, David.Castells, Jordi.Carrabina}@UAB.es)

sorting. The following one introduces our proposal and describes the basic PE. After that, we shall describe the results of implementing the sorter on a reconfigurable platform and compare it to other sorters in literature. Finally, the concluding section outlines the main contribution of this work and foresees its continuation lines.

II. PREVIOUS HARDWARE ARCHITECTURES

Most hardware sorters are inspired on parallel sorting algorithms. In fact, such algorithms rely on a number of processors so to diminish the time to do the sorting. It is known that *quicksort*, *mergesort*, and *heapsort* have an average time complexity of $O(n \log n)$ to sort n data and use, of course, a single processor. The work (time multiplied by the number of processors) of a parallel algorithm might be equally optimal while reducing the total time devoted to sorting.

To translate parallel sorting algorithms into pure hardware with a reasonable overhead, processors must be simple enough. On the other hand, memory elements and interconnections must be dedicated to avoid conflicts of accessing shared elements [15].

Common architectures to support parallel sorting algorithms are based on a very simple PE that we shall refer to as *2-sorter*. This PE (see fig. 1) includes two data registers as memory elements and, as its name says, sorts two input data and stores the result into the output registers. It can sort in an ascending or descending manner, depending on a control input d , which we shall see that is not always included because the circuit topology usually determines which type of sorting has to do.

The following is devoted to explain several solutions to build efficient hardware sorters.

Fig. 1. A 2-sorter. Optional input d determines if sorting is done in ascending or descending form. Dotted line indicates a possible feedback that is used in some architectures.

A. Sorting Networks

A sorting network S_n is a net of PE able to sort n data. Clearly, the 2-sorter is a S_2 sorting network, and it is possible to build any S_n from S_2 or S_1 . Any larger network S_{n+1} can be constructed from S_n by a simple induction rule. Fig. 2(a) and 2(b) illustrate the rules for parallel selection and insertion sorters. Assume that data must be sorted in a descending order from top to bottom. In case (a), the 2-sorters are cascaded along the $n+1$ inputs so that the greatest data is put at the bottom; i.e., the greatest data is selected. The left n data is fed into the S_n sorter that works similarly. On the other hand, in case (b) a new data is inserted to the previously ordered n data. The cascade of 2-sorters will interchange inputs at outputs while the lower position data is less than the upper one; i.e., the new data causes a cascade of interchanges up to the insertion point.

The final structure for either sorting network is the same. Both require $n(n-1)/2$ 2-sorters and have a maximum depth of $2n-3$ for $n > 2$. The depth of a sorting network is the number of 2-sorters that data goes through. The work of such networks is, then, $O(n^3)$, which is clearly poorer than simple insert or selection sorting sequential algorithms.

However, they have been improved by using merging networks. A merging network takes two ordered lists of data and produces a sorted list out of them. Merging networks can be done in different forms that can be derived from different induction rules. The induction rules have a merging network of 2 elements M_2 as the trivial case. (The 2-sorter can be viewed as a M_2 that merges a couple of single element lists.)

Fig. 2(c) illustrates one of such merging network types that performs a *perfect shuffle* on their input lists; i.e., the odd position elements of both input lists are merged apart from the even position ones, and combined afterwards. Provided that input lists are ordered, it is proven that all data after such a perfect shuffle is either at its final position or at a distance 1 depending on their counterparts from the opposite merging list (i.e., the odd or the even-position data). Therefore, an additional column of 2-sorters must be used to place every element at its final, ordered position.

Fig. 2. Sorting networks: (a) and (b) sort by selection and insertion, respectively; (c) is a merging network; and (d) is an improved sorting network due to Batcher.

The number of 2-sorters involved in a merging network M_n is $s(n) = 1 + n \log n$ and its depth is $d(n) = 1 + \log n$, which can be derived from:

$$\begin{cases} s(2n) = 2s(n) + n/2 - 1 \\ d(2n) = 1 + d(n) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Merging and sorting networks can be combined to significantly improve the cost figures of the simple sorting networks already described.

Fig. 2(d) illustrates the inductive structure of a sorting network S_{2n} built from two S_n and a merging network M_{2n} . This divide-and-conquer approach stops at S_2 ; i.e. at 2-sorters. The number of 2-sorters required is $\Theta(n \log^2 n)$, and the depth of such networks is $\Theta(\log^2 n)$.

For obvious reasons, these networks are named odd-even merging (or sorting) networks, discovered by Batcher in 1964 [3]. To simplify interconnects, he also presented an additional network, called *bitonic merger*, that had similar cost figures (similar complexity order, worst complexity constants).

Further improvements can be achieved with respect to parallel sorting algorithms [9] but at the cost of increasing PE and interconnection complexities, which make them difficult to translate into pure hardware solutions.

With hardware implementation in mind, the odd-even merging network might have a size in terms of 2-sorters much too big to fit in a single chip. Consequently, some area-saving solution must be adopted.

In [12]–[13] a kind of “network folding” is proposed so data are recirculated through the net at the cost of adding some switching circuitry and with the penalty of time complexity, which is augmented in the same proportion as network is folded.

The next subsection is devoted to a different type of solution that looks for simplification at the cost of time efficiency, again.

B. Linear Arrays

The size of a network is critical because it determines whether it can be implemented in a single chip. Furthermore, interconnectivity and control of such networks must be reduced to minimize the area overhead.

As a result, sorting circuits must take into account not only complexity issues but area limitations too. In fact, they can be regarded as dedicated processors in a specialized parallel machine for sorting.

The size an odd-even sorting network S_n is $\Theta(n \log^2 n)$ which means that there should be $\log^2 n$ columns of n 2-sorters. The size of a 2-sorter depends on the data length in bits so that the multiplying constants in the size complexity grows in the same proportion. Consequently, it is not always possible to fit all the $\log^2 n$ columns of a full odd-even network.

A solution to such a problem comes from using only a few of the total $\log^2 n$ columns. Of course, such approach is only of interest when $\log^2 n \gg 1$, which clearly occurs in most of the cases.

Though there are other approaches [16], for simplicity, we shall limit the following discussion to the use of columns that are inspired in structures of 2-sorters as depicted in Fig. 2(a) and 2(b). Note that odd-even mergers have quite different columns along the array, and, significantly, the connections among their elements require an additional switching network.

Each column has a constant size of n 2-sorters and a unitary depth. Notice that the work to sort n data requires $n-1$ insertions (or selections) that reuse the 2-sorters in the column. As a result, the work is $\Theta(n^2)$; i.e. similar to that of the simple sequential sorting algorithms. However, though not efficient in time, sorters based on this principle do not take as much area as a full (or folded) sorting network.

In [14] the authors propose a sorter architecture that uses a column of n 2-sorters to progressively sort n data. The 2-sorters (see Fig. 1) include a feed-back loop to output only the greatest or lesser value, and a control input to determine the operation mode (ascending or descending). These modules are denominated compare-swap (CS) cells. They are layout in cascade so their outputs are attached to the inputs of their successors.

At each clock cycle, every CS cell in the column compares the incoming value B to the internal one A so that A is either shifted to the successor cell or held (in these cases, input data B is placed at output registers Y).

To correctly sort data, registers must be reset. The reset is done by feeding the first cell with n null data (zeros) in a descending mode, and n more in the opposite one. After such a reset, the n data are input in series so they are progressively put in the corresponding A registers. To ensure that no datum is in a B register, a series of n null data must be entered in the input port of the structure. Finally, to obtain the sorted list at the output port, n zeros are input in the ascending mode. Notice that these two last steps of the sorting procedure are equivalent to the initial resetting. Therefore, the time to sort a list of n data is $4n$.

Though some control is needed to manage the result sorting network, it can easily be implemented by a simple FSM.

The size of this sorter circuit is $s(n) = n$ and the maximum depth is $d(n^*) = 2n^*$, where n^* stands for all input data, including zeros, thus $n^* = 4n$. The sorting work is equal to $4n^2$. However, it is important to recall that has an expandable architecture and able to take the n best scores out of a much larger number of them.

The next section is devoted to present our approach to this problem, which is similar to this of using a single column of a full sorting network but differs in the basic building block, which is not the 2-sorter.

III. PROGRAMMABLE REGISTER FILE FOR INSERTION SORT

The insertion sort algorithm is a well-known one that repeats for every unsorted datum the same procedure which is of looking for its position in the sorted list and inserting it there. The corresponding algorithm is presented in the next code.

```

for each unsorted  $D$  {
   $i = 0$ ;
  while( ( $i < n$ ) && ( $D > R[i]$ ) ) {
     $R[i] = R[i+1]$ ;
     $i = i+1$ ;
  } /* while */
   $R[i-1] = D$ ;
} /* for */

```

For the sake of simplicity, the previous algorithm sorts data in an ascending form, and considers that $R[n]$ does exist and is equal to ∞ . It is easily converted into a parallel one, provided that the `while` is transformed in a bounded iteration and its body executed only when the second term in the original condition applies:

```

for each unsorted  $D$  {
  for(  $i = 0$ ;  $i < n$ ;  $i = i+1$  ) {
    if(  $D > R[i]$  ) {
       $R[i] = R[i+1]$ ;
    } /* if */
    if(  $D \leq R[i+1]$  ) {
       $R[i] = D$ ;
    } /* if */
  } /* for */
} /* for */

```

Note that the last assignment has to be moved inside the body of the `for` loop. The functionality, though, is the same. The inner `for` is a possible source of parallelism. As its body depends on local computations, a set of n simple PE are able to do the job in a single step. The behavior of such a PE is, in fact, described in the body statements.

Assuming that every such PEs contain a register for a given data, the resulting register file (Fig. 3) is a simple linear structure that is easily expandable and requires no control at all. For each incoming data D , PEs in the register file either hold their previous value or take the successor's one. There is only one PE for which both conditions in the loop's body satisfy: the one in the insertion point. We shall see that its behavior is equivalent to the shifting PEs.

Sorters built upon this architecture have a linear size and a unitary depth. Thus the work to sort n data is n^2 . As with the previous column-based sorters, the main advantage is that is easily fitted in a chip because of simplicity and expandable architecture.

The next section is devoted to describe the PE structure of these sorters.

Fig. 3. Architecture of a register file for insertion sort.

TABLE I
LOGIC FUNCTION OF DATA-SLICE MODULES

p_i	p_{i+1}	shift	load	hold
0	0	1	0	0
0	1	0	1	0
1	0	-	-	(1)
1	1	0	0	1

IV. DATA-SLICE MODULE

The programmable register file structure required for insert sort can easily be built upon a PE that performs three functions: hold, shift, and load data. In a given clock cycle, only a module can load the incoming data, the modules at the left register shift and the right part holds its contents (see Fig. 3).

Table I shows the logic function of data-slice modules and, from it, the result load value into the corresponding register:

$$R_i^+ = p_i \cdot R_i + \overline{p_i} (p_{i+1} D + \overline{p_{i+1}} R_{i+1}) \quad (2)$$

where p_i corresponds to $R_i \geq D$; i.e. to the condition that determines if D should be placed at the left ($p_i = 1$) or at the right ($p_i = 0$). The latter case implies doing a left shift or loading D . Such a decision depends on p_{i+1} so, from the i -th PE, it can be viewed similarly; i.e., as performing a left shift. The last module takes $p_n = 1$, as no datum can be placed at its right.

For practical reasons, computation of load data D_i is placed at corresponding modules and the result sent to their left, i.e.:

$$\begin{cases} R_i^+ = p_i \cdot R_i + \overline{p_i} D_{i+1} \\ D_{i+1} = (p_{i+1} D + \overline{p_{i+1}} R_{i+1}) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

As a result, each module (Fig. 4) contains a k -bit wide number comparator, one register of the same size, and a 2-1 multiplexer for words of k -bits. The logic to determine where the new data should be placed (on the left or right part of the i -th position) can be performed with the control lines of the MUX.

Compared to 2-sorters, these modules have a only single comparators and registers, thus being simpler and cheaper.

Fig. 5 shows the data-slice architecture of sorters based on these modules. Connectivity of modules is, as in sorters based in 2-sortes, local with the exception of input data D . Similarly, little global control circuitry is required to operate

Fig. 4. Data-slice module of the insert sort register file.

Fig. 5. Linear composition of n data-slice modules.

the sorters, and certainly less than the column-based ones. In terms of expandability both approaches outcome network sorters.

V. RESULTS

In this section we shall discuss the cost figures of the proposed insertion sorter architecture and compare them to other sorters; particularly, to odd-even and bitonic merging networks, and to column sorters. As both types use different PE, the area shall be measured in number of comparators, registers and multiplexers.

Table II compares theoretical costs in terms of number or elements and time to sort a list of n -data of the different sorters analyzed in this paper. Our proposed sorter, as it is basically a register file with optional shifting, is denominated as “shifter”. Formulas show, undoubtedly, that shifting sorters improve column-based sorting. With respect to merging networks, they require more time and less area. However, shifting sorters have a worst work figure so they are only interesting when area is a critical factor and/or gradual sorting is required.

In [13] there are some proposals to fold sorting networks to diminish their area cost, but they equally multiply the time

TABLE II
COST OF SORTING LISTS OF n DATA

number of	bitonic	odd-even	column	shifter
MUX	$n (\log^2 n + \log n) / 2$	$n (\log^2 n - \log n + 4) / 2 - 2$	$2n$	n
CMP	$n (\log^2 n + \log n) / 4$	$n (\log^2 n - \log n + 4) / 4 - 1$	n	n
Registers	$n (\log^2 n + \log n) / 2$	$n (\log^2 n - \log n + 4) / 2 - 2$	$2n$	n
Clock cycles	$(\log^2 n + \log n) / 2$	$(\log^2 n + \log n) / 2$	$4n$	n

by the same proportion and include some area overhead due to increasing control complexity of the result network.

The main drawback of shifting and column sorters is that they cannot be pipelined as networks can. Once pipelined, sorting networks can take a block of n -data every clock cycle so that they apparently produce a list of sorted data per clock tick. Of course, they have a latency equivalent to the time shown in table II.

Real costs include placement & routing, which strongly depends on topology. In this aspect, linear arrays outperform networks because of their inherent simplicity.

Table III gives some performance measurements on implemented sorters. Data come from [8], [14], [18], and our own. We have implemented our shifting sorter on a Xilinx Virtex-II XC2V3000 FPGA to enable comparison to the rest, and especially to the odd-even merging network. Periodic sorting networks have been added because they are regular networks that enable simple controlling schemes when data are feed back to reuse a part of them. They are described in detail in the references given in the table. Each of these sorters sorts 32 16-bit numbers.

Operating frequencies strongly depend on the maximum combinational delay between clock ticks. The absence of interconnection logic enables all sorters work at the full speed of their basic building blocks. The relative simplicity of the proposed data-slice module (with respect to the 2-sorter) enables achieving faster sorters.

In either case, a careful design of the comparator may result in significant speedups. As for the synthesis of the shifting sorter, we had given priority to specification simplicity rather than to minimize the combinational delay of the comparator.

The synthesis results of the proposed sorter gave clock periods that threefold the minimum of the device.

At its maximum speed, the shifting sorter sorts the 32 numbers in 148nS, which is approximately a 160% more than the 95nS that takes to the odd-even merger to do the same job. However, it takes roughly 14 times more area than the shifting sorter (i.e. 41% of total FPGA area with respect to only 3%) thus making the latter more efficient for a single sort.

The capability of sorting networks of being pipelined makes linear array sorters less efficient in processing streams of blocks of n -data. Particularly, they still last n clock cycles to do the sorts whereas networks output a result at each one.

On the other hand, linear sorters as the shifting one take significantly less area, and are well-suited for sorting streams of single data. In fact, as they take only the n top data, they can be used in search procedures.

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE RESULTS

sorter	speed (MHz)	latency (ticks)	gate count	area of XC2V3000
bitonic	127	14	153k	43%
odd-even	147	14	137k	41%
periodic [10][17]	121	20	248k	70%
periodic [7]	152	20	223k	66%
column	66	32	23k	(core) 1.0x1.3mm ²
shifter	min.: 168 max.: 216	32	12k	3%

VI. CONCLUSION

Hardware sorters help to increase the performance of parallel sorting systems, which are and have been a matter of research whose importance increased in the recent years because of the ever-growing number of applications that deal with massive data (e.g. storage systems, data-base management, data-mining, communication, et cetera).

In this paper, we had analyzed some hardware sorters based on sorting networks and linear arrays. The surveyed architectures do use a basic PE that is denominated 2-sorter, but there are other approaches with different PE. In particular, one [16] uses a fairly complex PE in a linear array for implementing an insert sort based algorithm.

We have also proposed a new kind of linear array sorters based on programmable register files whose elements can optionally shift. Therefore, we named these sorting architectures as shifting sorters.

Shifting sorters are based on very simple PEs that drastically cut their cost with respect to other linear arrays solutions. Furthermore, the resulting architecture is easily expandable and requires minimum control logic to operate.

They are suitable for applications that require sorting small number of data, as a PE in larger sorting systems [4], or to perform selection of the best scores in searchers.

As one of the keys to efficiency of shifting sorters is the speed, we will try to improve comparators by specifically adapting them to the micro-architectures of the target FPGA.

In the short term, we will design architectures to combine a number of shifting sorters in order to reduce the total cost of sorting. In particular, we believe that simple linear or tree-like combinations of shifting sorters might satisfy the stringent requirements of applications that require a high throughput.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. G. Akl, *Parallel Sorting Algorithms*, Academic Press, 1985.
- [2] S. Azuma, T. Sakuma, T. Takeo, T. Ando, and K. Shirai, "High-Performance Sort Chip", *Hot Chips* 11, Aug. 1999.
- [3] K. E. Batcher, "Sorting Methods and their Applications," *AFIPS Spring Joint Computing Conference*, vol. 32, pp. 307-314, 1968.
- [4] M. Bednara, O. Beyer, J. Teich, and T. R. Wanka, "Tradeoff analysis and architecture design of a hybrid hardware/software sorter," *IEEE Int'l. Conf. on Application-Specific Systems, Architectures, and Processors (Proc. of)*, pp. 299-308, July 2000.
- [5] Bitton, DeWitt, Hsiao, and Menon, "A taxonomy of parallel sorting," *Computing Surveys*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 287-318, 1984.
- [6] G. Brassard, and P. Bratley, *Fundamentals of Algorithmics*. Prentice-Hall, 1997, ch. 11.
- [7] E. R. Canfield and S. G. Williamson, "A sequential sorting network analogous to the Batcher merge," *Linear and Multilinear Algebra*, n^o. 29, pp. 43-51, 1991.
- [8] K. Claessen, M. Sheeran, and S. Singh, "The Design and Verification of a Sorter Core," *11th Advanced Research Working Conference on Correct Hardware Design and Verification Methods (CHARME'01)*. Springer-Verlag Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Vol 2144, September 2001, pp. 355-369.
- [9] R. Cole, "Parallel merge sort," *SIAM Journal on Computing*, vol. 17, num. 4, pp. 770-785, 1988.
- [10] M. Dowd, Y. Perl, L. Rudolph, and M. Sacks, "The periodic balanced sorting network," *JACM*, n^o. 36, pp. 738-757, 1989.
- [11] R. Kannan, "A pipelined single-bit controlled sorting network with $O(N \log^2 N)$ bit complexity," *Sixteenth Annual Joint Conference of the IEEE Computer and Communications Societies. INFOCOM '97*. Proceedings IEEE, vol.1, pp. 253 - 260, April 1997.

- [12] J.-D. Lee, and K. E. Batcher, "Minimizing communication of a recirculating bitonic sorting network," *Proc. of International Conf. on Parallel Processing*, pp. I-251–I-254, 1996.
- [13] J.-D. Lee, and K. E. Batcher, "Minimizing communication in the bitonic sorter," *IEEE Trans. on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, vol. 11, no. 5, May 2000.
- [14] Chi-Sheng Lin, and Bin-Da Liu, "Design of a pipelined and expandable sorting architecture with simple control scheme," *IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems, 2002. ISCAS 2002*, vol. 4, pp. IV-217–IV-220, May 2002.
- [15] S. Olanu, M. C. Pinotti, and S. Q. Zheng, "An optimal hardware-algorithm for sorting using a fixed-size parallel sorting device," *IEEE Trans. on Computers*, vol. 49, no. 12, Dec. 2000.
- [16] B. Parhami, and D.-M. Kwai, "Data-driven control scheme for linear arrays. Application to a stable insertion sorter," *IEEE Trans. on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, vol. 10, pp.23–28, 1999.
- [17] M. Sheeran, "Sorts of butterflies," *Proc. 4th Banff Workshop on Higher Order*, Springer Workshops on Computing, G. Birtwistle, Ed. 1991.
- [18] —, *A Sorter Example in Lava*, www.xilinx.com, 2004.